

EXTRALINGUISTIC FEATURES OF FAMILY CONCEPT PHRASES IN THE FRENCH LANGUAGE*Maharramova G.**PhD student**Nakhchivan State University***Abstract**

The article explores the extralinguistic features of phraseologisms related to the family concept in the French language. The research examines how family-related phraseologisms are formed from social, cultural, and psychological aspects and how these phraseologisms are linked to external factors of the language. The aim is to analyze how phraseologisms expressing the family concept react not only to the internal structure of the language but also to the influence of society and culture. Emotional tones of phraseologisms, social stereotypes related to family relations, and family values in certain cultures are important elements that form the extralinguistic features of these phraseologisms. The article shows how phraseologisms reflecting various aspects of the family concept in the French language are strengthened and transformed in this socio-cultural context.

Keywords: Phraseology, extralinguistics, the concept of family, social factors, culture, psychological aspects.

Introduction

French is the official state language of the French Republic. It is one of the official languages of many international organizations, such as the United Nations (UN), the European Union, NATO, the International Red Cross, and many others. This ensures its important role in international diplomacy and relations. French is spoken not only in France but also in many countries around the world, especially in Africa, Canada, Belgium, Switzerland, Luxembourg, and other countries. Approximately 300 million people speak French. It is known as the language of rich literature, art, and culture. French literature is widely appreciated around the world, and the language also plays a significant role in art, philosophy, and science. French is particularly used in the humanities and social sciences, as well as in some technical fields. French universities and educational systems are attractive options for international students. Generally, French stands out on the world stage with its cultural and diplomatic importance and is widely used in various regions.

French is considered one of the most beautiful languages in the world, with a harmonic and melodic sound structure. It is not only the language of love but also of culture and art. Learning French immerses one in a world of beautiful words and sounds. When speaking French, one can feel the voice being softer and more melodic. Words in French are pronounced very clearly, and their pronunciation is very distinct. This language is also a powerful and highly expressive language of emotions.

French is not only a beautiful, musical language but also a necessary one for establishing connections and communication with various world nations. It plays an important role in establishing trade and cultural exchanges between different countries. Knowing French is very beneficial for business communication, tourism, academic research, and other fields.

French is the language of culture and art. French literature, cinema, music, and painting have always been in the spotlight. French is the language of many great works of world literature, such as "Madame Bovary," "The Count of Monte Cristo," "Journey to the Center of Africa," "Les Misérables," and other world-famous works. These works, written in this language,

continue to be read with interest and love by readers worldwide in the 21st century.

Famous for its beauty and elegance, French culture is the heritage of world culture. France is well-known for its heritage in art, architecture, cuisine, fashion, literature, and music. These elements make French culture beautiful and unique.

The cultural heritage of France has left an irreplaceable mark on world culture, and the elegance, magnificence, and beauty of French culture continue to inspire and captivate everyone who appreciates and values high artistry.

The French are considered sociable people who enjoy beauty and are capable of creating it. The French culture we are discussing is realized in the fixed expressions and phraseologisms of the language.

French phraseologisms not only carry linguistic features but also preserve extralinguistic factors. The extralinguistic aspect of language primarily refers to its connection with culture. The most fundamental indicator of the relationship between language and culture, traditions, and customs is the unique way the language organizes and conceptualizes the world. In recent linguistic literature, this is referred to as the linguistic landscape of the world. If we rank the language units in the linguistic landscape based on their reflection of culture, phraseologisms, proverbs, and sayings would occupy the top positions. If the linguistic landscape is created by human perceptions of the world, phraseological units arise from the views people have about the world. Phraseological combinations express the ethnic-cultural perceptions people have about the world. According to N. Jafarov, there is no language that does not have its own unique linguistic landscape. The same applies to the French people. Lexical units and phraseologisms reflecting the family concept in the French linguistic landscape form a special layer. Although the family concept phraseologisms found in the lexical layer of their language differ significantly from the thoughts and perceptions of Azerbaijanis, who have a different language and traditions and are geographically distant from the French, research shows that family is a value for all nations, including these two. Unfortunately, the value of this concept is diminishing not

only in France but also in other countries, including Azerbaijan.

In French society, the family is formed through marriage. In modern society, marriage can be official or religious. The fact that marriages are conducted through weddings and ceremonies indicates that the marriage of individuals forming a family is accepted and approved by society. The structure of the family changes over time and space. The number of family members and their roles within the family also vary from society to society. In rural areas, large families with high intergenerational interaction are more common. An extended family includes members such as parents, children, grandparents, etc. In a traditional family, multiple generations live together. A nuclear family consists of a mother, father, and child. In modern times, many people transitioning from traditional to nuclear families experience weakened kinship ties. Additionally, as the number of nuclear families increases, the rate of young people migrating to industrial centers also rises. Relationships between family members are reflected in language expressions. If we statistically analyze these expressions, phraseologisms would occupy the largest share. If we conduct a statistical study of the parts of speech that realize the family concept in modern French, we see that this concept is mostly realized through nouns, followed by adjectives, and then verbs. It is important to note that in the cognitive interpretation process, all obtained associations, including individual ones, are interpreted as cognitive features of the concept.

Let's look at the representation of the lexical unit "famille-family" in dictionaries. *Famille*-family, *en famille*-in one's circle, among themselves; *familler*- 1) close, familiar, friendly; 2) random, simple; 3) everyday, ordinary [5, p. 115].

In the explanatory dictionary of the French language, several words derived from the root "famille" are included. The lexical unit "famille-family" is given in four semantics:

1. Ensemble de ceux qui, vivants ou morts, sont liés par un lien de parenté (All persons, living or dead, who are related by kinship);
2. Ensemble constitué par le père, la mère et leurs enfants (Group consisting of father, mother, and their children);
3. Ensemble des enfants d'un couple (Children of a couple);
4. Ensemble d'êtres vivants ou d'objets ayant ensemble des caractères communs (Group of living beings or objects with common characteristics);
5. Avoir un air de famille, se ressembler (To resemble, to look like family) [2, p. 438].

Several lexical units with the same root as "famille" are also used in French.

Familiariser(se)- se familiariser avec qqc se rendre cette chose connue en la pratiquant régulièrement (bir şeylə tanış olmaq, müntəzəm olaraq məşq etməklə özünü tanıdın).

Familiarité- 1. Fait de rendre qqch. Familier par la pratique; 2. Comportement simple et amical

Familiartités-Façons indiscrettes ou inconvenantes—*Se laisser aller à des familiarités de langage*//*Avoir des familiarités avec une femme.*

Familièrement—de façon familière. Par exemple: *Le chef de l'état s'en tretint familièrement avec un simple citoyen.*

Familière, ère— I.

1. Qu'on est habitué à voir autour de soi, ou qui est habituel à qqn.(Ətrafımızda görməyə alışmışıq və ya kiməsə adi haldır);
2. Dont on a acquis la pratique, qu'on suit bien;
3. Dont les manières manquent de réserve, ou même qui se montre indiscret ou impoli avec les autres;
4. Se dit de ce qui est aimple et amical;
5. Qui appartient à la langue de la conversation.

Let us note that there are single expressions for many associations that realize the family concept.

II. Familier: Celui qui fréquente souvent une maison amie, un établissement: C'est un familier de la maison// Les familiers de ce café. [2, s.438]

We present the following single associations:

Nouns:

amis – friends, *arbre généalogique* – family tree, *bonheur* – happiness, *cadeaux* – gifts, *calin* – hug, *campagne* – countryside, *chaleur* – warmth, *chambre d'enfant* – children's room, *complicité* – complicity, *compréhension* – understanding, *confort* – comfort, *confortable* – comfortable, *convivialité* – sociability, *culture* – culture, *dispute* – argument, *divorce* – separation, *divorce*, *douleur* – pain, *euphorie* – euphoria, *femme* – woman, wife, *généalogie* – genealogy, *groupe* – group, *hétérosexuel* – heterosexual, *homme* – man, husband, *homosexuel* – homosexual, *intransigeance* – intransigence, uncompromising, *jeux* – games, *liens* – bonds, ties, *maison* – house, *origine* – origin, *paix* – peace, *parenté* – kinship, relatives, *père* – father, *problème* – problem, *proches* – close relatives, *regret* – regret, *relation* – relationship, *separation* – separation, *stabilité* – stability, *unité* – unity, *univers* – peace, *valeur* – value.

Adjectives and participles:

agréable – pleasant, *axée* – oriented, *calme* – calm, *élargie* – large, *extended*, *familiale* – family-related, *importante* – important, *inconditionnel* – unconditional, *mononucléaire* – single-nuclear family, *monoparentale* – single-parent family, *naturel* – natural, *nécessaire* – necessary, *recomposée* – reconstituted, *soudée* – closely-knit, *énervé* – to annoy, *partager* – to share, *protéger* – to protect, *sentir* – to feel.

When examining the lexical units realizing the family concept in modern French, we have identified the following features:

1) Language units realizing the concept of family composition: *enfants* – children, *parents* – parents, *frère* – brother, *soeur* – sister, *grands-parents* – grandparents, *père* – father, *homme* – man, husband, *femme* – woman, wife

2) Close relatives: uncle, aunt, their children – *cousins*, uncle – *oncle*, aunt – *tante*, close ones – *proches*, *kinship*, relatives – *parenté*

3) Family model: large family – *famille élargie*, single-nuclear family – *mononucléaire*, single-parent family – *monoparentale*, reconstituted family (family

with children from a previous marriage) – *recompose*, homosexual – *homosexuel*, heterosexual – *hétérosexuel*

4) Child and education: childhood – *enfance*, education – *éducation*, school – *école*, vacation – *vacances*, training – *apprentissage*, culture – *culture*

5) Support, mutual assistance: support – *soutien*, solidarity – *solidarité*, mutual assistance – *entraide*, security – *securité*, to protect – *protéger*, hug – *calin*, stability – *stabilité*, sociability – *convivialité*, calm – *calme*, to share – *partager*, understanding – *compréhension*

6) Love, friendly relations: love – *amour*, attachment – *affection*, warmth – *chaleur*, relationships – *relation*, friends – *amis*, bonds, ties – *liens*

7) Positive emotions, feelings: joy – *joie*, happiness – *bonheur*, euphoria – *euphorie*, comfort – *confort*, peace – *paix*, to feel – *sentir*, comfortable – *confortable*, pleasant – *agréable*, laughter – *rires*

8) Family traditions, joint activities: meal – *repas*, holidays – *fêtes*, Christmas – *Noël*, gifts – *cadeaux*, games – *jeux*

9) Negative emotions and feelings: *énervé* – to annoy, *intransigeance* – intransigence, uncompromising, *regret* – regret, *problème* – problem, *divorce* – separation, *séparation* – to separate, *douleur* – pain, *les pères et les enfants: la dispute* – fathers and children: argument. This refers to the lack of or loss of connections between children and parents.

10) Importance, significance: *importante* – important, *nécessaire* – necessary, *axée* – oriented, directed, *naturel* – natural, *valeur* – value

11) Housing, comfort: *foyer* – family home, *campagne* – countryside, *maison* – house, *chambre d'enfant* – children's room

12) Origin: *arbre généalogique* – family tree, *généalogie* – genealogy, *origine* – origin, etc. [4, p. 67]

The number of associations obtained during the research allows us to conclude that the concept of "famille-family" in French linguoculturology has a wide associative field. The most common and stable associations are: *amour*-love, *enfants*-children, *parents*-parents, *soutien*-support, *solidarité*-solidarity association. Overall, 13 cognitive features have been identified, the most represented being "family composition," "support, mutual assistance," and "love, friendship." The presence of single associations related to family models (*famille mononucléaire*: nuclear family, *recomposée*: reconstituted family; *homosexuel*: homosexual, *hétérosexuel*: heterosexual) allows us to judge the differentiation of types of family relationships related to changes in modern French society.

The associative fields of phraseological units mentioned above are directly related to the internal form of the phraseological unit. The internal form of phraseological combinations contains traces of past cultures. This means that the analysis of the internal form in the linguocultural aspect particularly highlights the national-cultural characteristics of phraseological combinations in the French language. In this regard, the main content provisions of the description of the internal form of phraseological combinations can be considered as follows: the internal form of

phraseological combinations should be studied within the anthropological paradigm of knowledge, taking into account the relationship between the semantic structure of phraseological combinations and other components, and above all the motivation of the meaning of the phraseological combination and the speaker's evaluative-emotional attitude towards the reality indicated in the phraseological unit. The linguocultural study of the internal form of phraseological combinations is of special importance. The assimilation of the cultural connotation of phraseological units is essential to express linguocultural competence for representatives of the language community. Without knowing the main categories of the culture of one's linguistic ethnos, one cannot think about the world. The cultural essence obtained from the moment a person is born lies at the basis of understanding the world, concepts of life, death, fate, friendship, love, homeland, etc. Almost all such concepts form the basis of the internal form of phraseological units and appear in a national-characteristic form. Therefore, the interpretation of the cultural-national connotations of phraseological combinations aims to understand the deep features of the national mentality in the French language.

The use of various methods in the analysis of the internal form of phraseological combinations is associated with the complex nature of the described object - phraseological combinations of the French language.

The main parameters for describing the internal form of phraseological combinations in French include various intra-linguistic features, first of all, the internal form of phraseological combinations and different types of connections between macrocomponents and extralinguistic knowledge such as folklore texts, myths, legends, religious texts, etc. Especially, the history of the formation, etymology, traditions, lifestyle, ancient customs, historical events, etc. of phraseological combinations, referring to text sources containing household knowledge.

Phraseological units are linguistic structures that serve to convey certain concepts. There are many expressions in French phraseology that reflect national-cultural characteristics. Many of them reflect the perceptions of the French people, their culture, and their way of life.

Phraseologisms are stable expressions in the French language that reflect the French way of life and socio-cultural environment. Phraseologisms and idioms live and evolve together with the culture and linguistic memory of the respective people. They contain certain concepts and cultural codes. There are many phraseological expressions that generally describe the national character of the French, which are considered an important part of the linguistic heritage and a reflection of the mentality of the people. The French are a proud and sensitive nation. This characteristic is also reflected in the phraseological combinations in their language [6, p.193].

Thus, it is clear that any phraseological unit reflects the national identity and mentality of the people [3,p.98]. French phraseologisms are distinguished by

their elegance and delicate style, as well as by their high appreciation of intellectuals and love of luxury. In addition, the phraseological structure of the French language mainly reflects the myths and ideas about the French people, their national character, and their culture. They are part of the language and culture and are of great importance in studying the characteristics of the language.

"Most of the aspects accompanying the life of the nation – the place it inhabits, climate, religion, state institution, customs, and traditions can be to some extent external to it and probably possess special characteristics. There is only one phenomenon that is completely different in nature – the language, which is the breath of the nation, its spirit, is born with it" [1, p.142].

Phraseological expressions containing the concept of marriage: The basis of phraseological expressions related to the concept of "cohabitation" is usually built on the lexemes "mariage" - "marriage" and "ménage" - "household". However, the presence of any determinant gives these phraseological units a completely different meaning. The quantitative composition of nominations on this topic indicates that this phenomenon prevails in French society. As mentioned above, relations between men and women evolve with society, and the rules of behavior are dictated by time and social feelings. Naturally, in the 17th-19th centuries, social morality in unregistered relationships between men and women was not very strict, so there were several phraseological expressions used during that period: *être en conversation* (literally - to be in a criminal plan); *faire noce de chiens* (literally: - to make a dog wedding); *faux ménage* (literally - false household). These three phraseological units clearly reveal society's negative attitude towards this phenomenon, which also conditions the choice of "harsh" lexemes included in the above-mentioned phraseological units (crimonelle, faux). The presence of the "faux" (false, wrong) quality component in the last phraseological unit clearly demonstrates society's relentless resistance to moral freedom and its desire to emphasize the difference between "faux ménage" (illegal marriages) and "vrai ménage" (legal marriages). The phraseological expression "faire noce de chiens" was recorded in the French language as early as the 17th century, where the component "noce de chiens" (literally: - dog wedding) meant "sexual relations," and the whole expression stylistically had a derogatory character as it characterized relationships based solely on physical interest in a partner [8].

The following phraseological expression indicates the short-term nature of relationships formed in a military garrison: *-mariage de garnison-* (literally: - garrison marriage).

Some phraseological expressions are based on a semantically similar metaphor: *mariage à la colle* = *ménage à la colle* (literally - household with glue); *mariage à la détrempe*, a similar wordplay based on the model "à la colle" - literally: - marriage with glue paint. This phraseological combination is used to describe short-term and unserious marriages.

These two phraseological units are based on the comparison of illegal marriage to "household with glue" (*mariage à la colle*), where "la colle" (literally: glue) acts as a derivative of the verb "-se coller-." By the mid-18th century, the expression "être coller" began to be used in the sense of "cohabitation." Before that, this verb appeared as part of the free expression "coller sa peau" (literally: stick with the skin, stick with the whole body) with a more pronounced pejorative stylistic meaning [7, p.10].

The development history of the capital of France, Paris, is reflected in the following family concept phraseological units: *mariage de XIII arrondissement // mariage fait à la mairie de XXI* (literally - marriage contracted in the 13th arrondissement). At the time of the creation of this phraseological unit, there were 12 arrondissements in Paris, but now there are 20 in this city, and since the 13th arrondissement is the Chinatown, this phraseological unit can be considered an archaic expression. Another phrase – *mariage fait à la mairie de XXI* (literally - marriage contracted at the 21st town hall) reflects the current stage of the city's development.

The following phraseological units also exhibit full compatibility: *vivre maritalement* (to live in an unofficial marriage); *ménage à trois* (love triangle); *mariage du côté gauche* = *mariage de la main gauche* (literally - marriage on the left side / defect on the left hand). In French culture, the hand is a symbol of marriage relations ("*demande la main*" - to ask for the hand) and the ring, which serves as proof of the marriage bond, is worn on the right hand. Thus, the right hand is traditionally used to denote a legal marriage, while the left hand is used to denote unofficial cohabitation.

The extralinguistic characteristics of the language are clearly reflected in the following phraseological expressions meaning "happy marriage": *mariage d'amitié* (marriage based on mutual desire); *mariage d'amour* (marriage with love); *beau mariage* (happy marriage); *bon mariage* (profitable marriage) [9, p.77]. In the expression "bon mariage" (literally - good marriage, profitable marriage), one can clearly see the French capitalist mindset. Here, it is possible to observe the traditions of profit-seeking marriages and the tendency to calculate and save in capitalist society.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the love model has served to create new rules of relationships, words, and actions included in the ritual, and through them, corresponding views have been disseminated to increasingly wider segments of society. This model, as always, primarily evolves in aristocratic circles and then gradually penetrates the lowest levels of social structure. This is how the type of relationships between genders typical of Western society has formed. Even today, despite significant changes in this area, the remarkable feature of European civilization is the traditions inherited from courtly love. By analyzing the phraseological composition of the language both synchronically and diachronically, it is possible to obtain very interesting information that shows the

traditions of male and female relationships considered as a historical segment of its development in society.

Thus, language does not only serve to reflect what exists in culture but also grows within it, creating the culture itself. The language that creates the culture also develops within the culture.

References

1. Jafarov N. (2021). *Linguoculturology. Multidisciplinary Linguistics*. Baku: Science and education.
2. Dubois J. (1988). *Petit dictionnaire de la langue française*. Paris: Librairie Larousse.
3. Mahmudova Q. (2009). *Phraseology of the Kipchak Group of Turkic Languages*. Baku: Nurlan.
4. Baroshi V. (2002). *Phraseologisms of the French Language*. Etinger:Ural Publishing House.
5. Vygodskaya K.S. (1962). *French-Russian Dictionary*. Moscow: State Publishing House of Foreign and National Dictionaries.
6. Lyubart M.K. (2005). *The Family in French Society. Late XVIII – Early XX*. Moscow: Nauka.
7. Pushkarev G. A., Podkovyrova, I. V., Pushkareva, O. V. (2024). *The Family in the Proverbs of the Russian and French People*. Text: Direct // Young Scientist. No. 1 (75). pp. 9-15. [Electronic resource] <https://moluch.ru/young/archive/75/4000/>
8. Khamidova N. *Phraseologisms of the French Language and Their Classification* [Electronic resource] <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/frazeologizmy-frantsuzskogo-yazyka-i-ih-klassifikatsiya>
9. Chekalina E.M., Ushakova, T.M. (1998). *Lexicology of the French Language*. Publishing House of St. Petersburg University.